

Bonded Restorations

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Abstract

Restorative procedures are accompanied by the reduction of tooth stability, decrease of the fracture resistance, and an increase in deflection of weakened cusps. The choice between a direct or an indirect restorative technique, mainly in the posterior areas, is a challenge, and involves biomechanical, anatomical, functional, esthetic, and financial considerations. Bonded restorations provide long-term solutions that can restore the functions of the teeth and their esthetics. Preservation of sound enamel is one of the major concerns in adhesive dentistry. Following the biomimetic principles, employing minimally invasive applications and adhesive technologies is of paramount importance for successful restorations. The concept 'Minimally Invasive Dentistry' can be maximal preservation of healthy dental structures. In cariology, this approach encompasses the use of comprehensive information and methods, from accurate caries diagnosis and risk assessment to preventive measures and restoration repair techniques. Although minimally invasive restorative methods are widely accepted, noninvasive approaches remain a topic of debate. This review aims to explore the concept of partially bonded indirect restorations, addressing the drawbacks of traditional restorations, such as negative effects on periodontal health due to excessive contouring and overhanging ceramic. It also introduces a new approach for evaluating the quality and longevity of partial bonded restorations.

Keywords: Ceramics, Partially bonded restorations, Veneers, Tabletops.

Introduction

The main goal of dental restoration is to effectively restore the form, function, and appearance of the tooth. With advancements in modern dental materials, both patients and practitioners now have a variety of options to create restorations that are not only more functional but also more aesthetically natural¹.

Direct restorative procedures are performed directly within the oral cavity, using both esthetic and non-esthetic materials. These restorations can often be completed in a single visit, but they do not enhance the strength of the remaining tooth structure². When there is significant loss of tooth structure, restorative materials should be chosen for their ability to distribute stress effectively and must be carefully bonded to the remaining tooth. In such cases, materials may need to be fabricated outside the mouth in a laboratory and later bonded or cemented to the prepared cavity. This approach is known as indirect restorative procedures, with common examples including inlays, onlays, crowns, bridges, and veneers¹.

Advancements in dental materials and adhesive systems have significantly improved the ability to create restorations that cover only the damaged portions of teeth. These modern materials are designed to closely mimic the natural tooth structure in terms of both appearance and function. Enhanced adhesive systems enable these restorations to bond securely to the tooth, reducing the need for extensive preparation or removal of healthy tooth structure for retention. This approach conserves more of the natural tooth, leading to more conservative and effective dental treatments. However, in addition to advancements in materials, it is essential to implement conservative dental procedures to achieve optimal results³. Conservative treatments focus on minimizing the removal of healthy tooth structure and ensuring that the margins of restorations are placed at the supragingival

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level. These methods help preserve the integrity of the natural tooth, promote better long-term dental health, and provide more aesthetically pleasing outcomes.

In cases of extensively damaged teeth, a direct restorative approach has traditionally been the standard, though it often compromises the restoration's retention and the proper formation of contours. Recently, indirect partial coverage restorative techniques have gained acceptance. These methods preserve the remaining tooth structure while repairing the damaged areas, enhancing both function and aesthetics of the tooth. By providing better contour and fit, indirect restorations help restore the tooth's integrity and appearance more effectively.

Restorative processes can reduce tooth stability, decrease fracture resistance, and increase the risk of diverting weak cusps. This challenge is particularly pronounced in the posterior region, where both direct and indirect techniques present difficulties. These challenges arise due to the need to balance biomechanics, anatomy, function, aesthetics, and financial considerations. Therefore, choosing the appropriate restorative method in this region involves careful assessment of these factors to ensure long-term success and patient satisfaction⁴.

Restorative solutions that are partially bonded are probably also long-lasting options that restore the teeth's natural characteristics and appearance. The success of restoration depends on the application of adhesive technology and minimally invasive treatments, according to biomimetic guidelines. Because the over-contouring and overhangs of ceramic restorations in standard preparations negatively impact periodontal health, a new method was proposed to assess the longevity and quality of restorations using a partial bonding technique.

Various Partial Bonded Restorations Porcelain Veneers

Fig:1 Porcelain Veneers

Enamel translucency is crucial for achieving a natural look in dental restorations, and dental porcelain is particularly effective at replicating this feature. Porcelain veneers are valued for their ability to closely mimic the translucency of natural enamel, which helps create a realistic and appealing smile⁵.

These veneers offer a versatile solution for various cosmetic concerns, including altering the color, shape, and surface

texture of teeth, as well as closing gaps between them to improve overall appearance. Besides their aesthetic benefits, porcelain veneers are durable and resistant to stains from food and beverages, making them a practical choice for front teeth. Additionally, veneers are less invasive compared to full-coverage crowns, as they require minimal removal of natural tooth structure. They are applied as thin porcelain layers on the front surfaces of the teeth, which helps preserve more of the original tooth. Porcelain also has a thermal expansion rate similar to that of natural teeth, ensuring that veneers remain stable and function well under different temperature conditions.

When preparing a tooth for a veneer, the labial surface is reduced by 0.3 to 0.7 mm. The cavity depth is adjusted to the enamel level to ensure strong bonding between the veneer and the healthy tooth structure. To accommodate changes in tooth length, a 1.5 mm incisal clearance is provided. Porcelain veneers are retention-free restorations, relying solely on adhesive bonding to stay in place. The longevity of the veneer largely depends on the effectiveness of the bonding process and the technique employed⁶.

Non-prep veneers (Lumineers)

Fig 2: Lumineers

A different type of veneer, called Lumineers, is a brand of veneer only offered by some dentists and manufactured by a few dental laboratories. Lumineers are a thinner, more affordable, and quicker option compared to traditional veneers. They require less preparation of the teeth, making them a potentially reversible treatment. However, they generally don't last as long as traditional veneers and are less effective at concealing severe stains or discoloration.

The application process for Lumineers is simpler and faster. During the initial appointment, there is no need for extensive trimming or preparation of the teeth—only an impression is taken. This impression is then sent to a dental lab, where the custom Lumineers are created within about 2 to 4 weeks. Unlike with traditional veneers, there is no need for temporary veneers while the Lumineers are being made⁷.

In the second appointment, the Lumineers are bonded to the teeth. They are considered semi-permanent, meaning they can be removed with minimal damage to the underlying teeth if needed. However, similar to traditional veneers, Lumineers can make it more challenging to clean around the gum line, which could increase the risk of gum disease.

Partially coverage restorations

Managing partial restorations differs significantly from handling full coverage crowns. With partial restorations, only the damaged portion of the tooth is removed, leaving the surrounding healthy tooth structure intact. When a cavity extends more than one-third of the distance from the cusp tip toward the groove, special attention is required to protect the weakened tooth structure, particularly the cusps.

For functional cusps, a shoulder margin is used in the restoration. This margin extends 1 mm over the height of the axial wall to ensure that the cusp is adequately covered and protected. This approach helps to maintain the integrity and function of the tooth while addressing the damage effectively.

Inlay

Fig 3: Inlay

Inlays are used when it is challenging to achieve a proper contour, contact point, or occlusion with a direct restoration. They are also helpful if a directly placed restoration frequently fractures, as they can offer enhanced durability, with gold inlays being particularly strong. For those prioritizing aesthetics, composite and ceramic inlays are preferred, especially in visible areas like the mesial surfaces of upper premolars and the occlusal surfaces of lower teeth, where the appearance matters. Additionally, patients who are concerned about the appearance of amalgam restorations or who experience rare reactions, such as lichenoid reactions, might request alternative options. In these cases, inlays provide a suitable replacement, offering both functional and aesthetic advantages³.

Onlays

Fig 4: Onlay

Onlays are partial coverage restorations applied to protect weakened tooth structure without requiring extensive removal of healthy tooth material. They are commonly used

for posterior teeth that have undergone root canal treatment, as these teeth often need additional support due to weakened cusps and substantial structural loss. The root canal process removes part of the tooth's pulp chamber, further weakening the tooth and potentially leaving minimal buccal and lingual tooth structure. If this structure were entirely removed to accommodate a crown, the tooth might be less stable. By using an onlay, some of the buccal and lingual tooth structure can be preserved, which helps maintain the core of the tooth and reduces the necessity for a post, particularly in premolar teeth⁸.

Overlay

Fig 5: Overlay

An overlay is defined as a prosthesis restoring that restores the integrity of the occlusal cusps of a tooth. An overlay, sometimes called a partial crown in international literature, extends beyond the occlusal table and has peripheral boundaries that are distinctly supragingival, unlike conventional crowns.

Grooves on the occlusal surface are typically prepared to a depth of 1 mm to 1.5 mm during the mock-up process. A uniform reduction is performed on the occlusal surface, generally up to 2 mm. To protect the newly exposed dentin, a hybrid composite build-up is applied. This build-up seals the dentin, corrects the preparation's form, and removes any undercuts. The proximal "boxes" are prepared with either a butt joint or a rounded internal angle shoulder, with thickness ranging from 1 mm to 1.5 mm. The internal walls of these preparations are designed to be sharp and are vertically divergent, angling between 6 and 15 degrees⁹.

Veneerlay

Fig 6: Veneerlay

Veneerlays are a combination of onlay and buccal veneer, the term was first used by Edward McLaren et al who used a monolithic structure fabricated from lithium disilicate in maxillary bicuspid region. They are primarily used for posterior teeth affected by caries on the occlusal and buccal surfaces, as well as for patients with occlusal wear in these teeth. The design can vary in terms of occlusal coverage, thickness, and peripheral coverage. This approach is more conservative regarding the surrounding tissues, relying heavily on the thickness of the occlusal table. More conservative in nature for the tissues as it is more dependent on the occlusal table thickness. According to Dr. Olivier Etienne's 2019 guidelines, the design of veneerlay formations should feature rounded internal transitions. For optimal resistance to occlusal forces, the minimum thickness should be maintained at 1.5 mm, while for vestibular aesthetics, a thickness of at least 0.6 mm is recommended³.

Tabletop

Fig 7: Tabletop

A table top is a type of overlay because it is a partial restoration bonded to cover all the cusps. However, it is more tissue-conservative because it only addresses the thickness of the occlusal table. These restorations, also known as occlusal veneers, are frequently used to manage wear on extensive occlusal surfaces of posterior teeth.

These restorations are a type of overlay that serves as a partial bonded restorations, covering most of the cusps of the teeth. They are often used to address damage caused by bruxism, which involves clenching of the teeth, typically during sleep. This constant pressure can erode the occlusal surfaces and incisal edges of the teeth, potentially leading to severe damage and affecting the nerve. Prior to treatment, a diagnostic wax-up is essential to determine the appropriate height of the restorations, ensuring they meet both functional and aesthetic requirements¹⁰.

Intracuspoid Table Tops are used when the cusps are not significantly affected by abrasion. When preparing the surface with a round bur, it should stop about 1 millimeter away from the cusp tip, focusing mainly on the proximal ridges.

Tabletops (Cuspidial) are employed in cases of severe and widespread abrasion, where the palatal cusp is flattened, while the vestibular cusp remains intact. During preparation, the round bur should stop 1 millimeter from the tip of the vestibular cusp. The buccal cusp's form is preserved to maintain the facial aesthetics. The preparation should also include the palatal cusp to restore its proper shape, and the tabletop is positioned on the proximal ridges³.

Fabrication and bonding of partial bonded restorations

Ceramic: The impression for the restoration is taken using both heavy and light body silicone, and the shade is selected with a Vitapan 3D Master shade guide. The restoration is then designed and fabricated using CAD/CAM technology. After the try-in stage, the framework is covered with a compatible porcelain system, with a thickness ranging from 1 mm to 2 mm. An aesthetic try-in of the restorations is conducted before final staining and glazing.

Following the try-in, the restoration is rinsed, air-dried, and treated with Ivoclean (Ivoclar Vivadent), allowing it to react with the inner surface for 20 seconds. It is then rinsed and dried again before applying Monobond Plus (a silane coupling agent) over the entire inner surface of the restoration, which is left to react for 60 seconds before the excess liquid is air-dried. The restoration is now ready for cementation.

The tooth is etched with 37% phosphoric acid for 15 seconds, rinsed, and then coated with a thin layer of bonding agent, which is polymerized for 15 seconds. A layer of resin cement (Multi-Link N) is applied to the prosthesis in a luting consistency. The restoration is then seated, and any excess luting cement is removed. While supporting the restoration, the resin cement is cured. After a spot cure, any remaining excess cement is cleaned up. Light curing is performed according to the resin manufacturer's instructions³.

Lithium Disilicate: The procedure for creating impressions and restorations involves similar steps, utilizing CAD / CAM technology, 3D printing, and milling. For bonding e.max veneers, the process begins with etching the veneer using Ivoclean for 20 seconds, followed by rinsing and air-drying. Next, a thin layer of Monobond Plus silane coupling agent is applied to the veneer and left for 1-2 minutes. Adhesive is then applied to the tooth; if the adhesive is thin and non-filled, it can be light-cured, but if it is thick and filled (such as Opti Bond FL), it should remain non-polymerized. Finally, the veneer is luted with light-cured resin cement.

Understanding and preventing clinical failures in adhesive restorations, particularly in root-canal treated teeth, is crucial. Common causes of failure include recurring caries, hypersensitivity due to erosion, pulp issues, and mechanical problems like fractures or chipping of ceramic materials. These failures can hinder tooth healing and maintenance, leading to potential tooth loss¹¹.

Research has shown that the lifespan of posterior teeth depends on the remaining natural tooth structure and changes in dentin over time. Full-coverage crowns were traditionally used for endodontically treated teeth, with studies from 2002 indicating that covering the cusps could significantly improve the survival rate of non-vital posterior teeth¹². However, this

approach often removed a substantial amount of healthy tooth structure. Modern practices now favor partial bonded restorations-such as inlays, onlays, overlays, and tabletops-because they better preserve healthy tissue and provide effective alternatives to full crowns, with their success dependent on the remaining tooth structure and adhesive bonding effectiveness³.

Conclusion

Partial bonded restorations are a minimally invasive treatment that maintains the natural form of the tooth while providing an aesthetically pleasing result. These restorations are designed to preserve as much of the original tooth structure as possible, which is often preferable to using artificial materials. They not only ensure the tooth's mechanical functionality and stability but also deliver a natural-looking outcome. Furthermore, partial bonded restorations are generally more affordable compared to traditional full crown restorations, making them an attractive option for patients.

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